

NISE DA SILVEIRA AND PSYCHIATRY IN BRAZIL IN THE MILITARY REGIME (1964 - 1985)

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8127216

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ABSTRACT

This text addresses the theme of 'Nise da Silveira and psychiatry in Military Brazil (1964-1985)'. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it broadens knowledge about one of the important psychiatrists in the history of Brazilian medicine. Its social relevance lies in presenting to the general public the concepts and forms of scientific work adopted by the physician. Its general objective is to carry out a study about the life of Nise da Silveira, correlating her psychiatric work with the moment of military dictatorship in the country. As an investigative method, a bibliographic research will be carried out, taking a materialist-dialectical approach as a way of revealing the internal and of the object to be studied, its causes and consequences. Nise da Silveira represents a milestone in the history of humanized psychiatric treatment given to citizens considered insane. During the military regime many hospitals were created, exponentially increasing the number of inmates. During this period of military dictatorship, many people were imprisoned in asylums as a way to silence their voices against the regime. Care for the mentally ill in Brazil and severe changes from the work of Nise da Silveira when the issue of awareness and breaking of myths and taboos began to be worked on, in which the aim was to merge Occupational Therapy with art, allowing the sick expressed their inner worlds through painting.

Keywords: Nise da Silveira. Psychiatry in Brazil. Military regime.

INTRODUCTION

Nise da Silveira (1906-1999) was one of the most important Brazilian psychiatrists, developing work in the fields of Psychopedagogy, when this technical term was not even thought of, and Occupational Therapy in psychiatric hospitals. His medical practice opposed the traditional model of psychiatric treatment, which used, among other things, electroshock, seeking to give dignity to individuals who had left asylums.

Nise's innovative technique, with regard to the humane treatment of inmates in hospices and mental hospitals, was applied at a time when Brazil is experiencing a period of social schizophrenia, caused by fear of the implementation of the regime and communist ideas in the country, and continues with his work throughout the period of the Military Regime, when, in the world of psychiatry, it was common to use shocks and abuse as the main instrument and technique for the treatment and [supposed] cure of inmates of asylum centers .

Nise da Silveira's life story as a psychiatric doctor is troubled, from the point of view of which she suffered a brutal interruption, somewhat suspicious, because without conditions to eliminate her from the technical point of view, she was accused of subversive links with communism, which led to her being imprisoned for a period of 16 months in the public jail on Rua Frei Caneca. Before his arrest, in 1933, he was an intern at Antônio Austregésilo's neurological clinic. In the same year, she was approved in a competitive examination to become a psychiatrist at the Hospital da Praia Vermelha, in the Service of Assistance to Psychopaths and Mental Prophylaxis.

During the period from 1937 to 1944, she lived in self-isolation and semi-clandestine, having her socio-political rights reestablished in 1946, when she began to work as a psychiatrist, in 1946, at the Pedro II National Psychiatric Center, in Rio de Janeiro, where he opposed the treatments intended for the patients collected there. As a form of punishment by the medical team, which considered such methods as electroshock, insulin therapy and, later, lobotomy, as the most effective in the treatment of madness, she was sent to the Center's Occupational Therapy treatment ward and there she was able to place putting into practice what he believed to be a more humanistic way of assisting inmates.

In an attempt to annul her action, they threw her into an uninteresting ward, for the psychiatrists, or into a ward where she would soon give up work. However, he did not give up and from then on used the possibility of art, more specifically, painting, as a form of treatment for the insane. He introduced animals into the process, dogs and cats.

She already came from a wide and long-term coexistence with several intellectuals and artists, which made it possible for her to follow this path, as an alternative treatment for those who were placed in asylums and forgotten by luck, by the State and by the compassion of doctors. of the time.

PSYCHIATRY IN BRAZIL

The objective of this text is to carry out an analysis of the madness and the role of Nise da Silveira in the period of the military dictatorship; However, for that, we consider it important to go back in time and return our analysis to a quick insertion in the history of the treatment given to the insane, because that way, one can have an approximate notion of what motivated the psychiatrist to intervene in a humanistic way in the care and in the attempt recovery of inmates.

Psychiatry in Brazil first emerged as a need to control social disorganization. With a large number of social degenerates who roamed the Brazilian colony, with a scarce and abandoned scenario. According to Machado (1978) Brazilian psychiatry was born “from medicine that incorporates society as a new object and imposes itself as an instance of social control of individuals and populations. It is within social medicine that psychiatry is constituted” (p. 376).

Understood in this way, Psychiatry at the time mentioned, played the role of a hygienist science, with the aim of keeping these decrepit figures out of the sight of society, because not being exposed to the eyes of all, the understanding that could be reached was that the problem did not exist. All of this was carried out with the connivance of the Portuguese Crown and the families, as well as under the auspices of society.

Several nursing homes functioned as asylums to receive these indigents and other indomitable figures, socially unwanted, such as prostitutes, drunks, single mothers whom the family wanted to deprive of the home. Sigaud, in his article on the Chamber of Rio de Janeiro, published in 1878, reports that,

In the interest of families, and for domestic tranquility, a special house dedicated to the reception and treatment of the insane would perform important services. In the interest of public morality, the confinement of maniacs would prevent, for once, the ridiculous scenes of certain madmen, and the indecent caricatures, which lithographs reproduce in thousands of copies (SIGAUD, 2005, p. 05).

The Santa Casas de Misericórdia, following the Portuguese paradigm and with the people who carried out the service work, also from Portugal, were philanthropic entities maintained by religious orders and confraternities, linked to the Catholic Church and with the support of the Portuguese Crown, which had as their attribution collaborate with the removal of the poor, insane, orphans and indigent from the streets of cities. In *Danação da Norma*, by Machado (1978), criticisms of the poor functioning of the institution managed by Santa Casa da Misericórdia address, among others, the problem of the mixed population of insane people, not separating the most critical cases from the less critical ones from a clinical point of view.

In this period of the history of psychiatry in Brazil,

The creation of the hospice complies with the requirement of only receiving insane and curable people; not to receive idiots, imbeciles, epileptics or paralytics, demented, who are incurable and can live with the family. That would be the ideal population. Removing the character of a specific place for curable insane people, the hospice becomes a charitable institution useful to society (PORTOCARRERO, 2002, p. 111).

Assistance to those considered crazy was through philanthropy and kindness. According to Piccinini (2017), assistance to the sick was provided by the Casas de Misericórdias spread across Brazil between the years 1543 to 1803. They believed that such charitable actions were carried out in order to remove those considered sick from society.

According to Medeiros (1987 *apud* PICCININI, 2017, p. 01) they fulfilled the corporal orders of mercy: “Educate the foundlings, free the captives, help the prisoners, cover the naked, feed the hungry, give drink to those who are thirsty, give accommodation to pilgrims, heal the sick, accompany and bury the dead.” The origin of the disease they carried in their body was not known exactly about the insane, who were normally forced to live away, exiled, excommunicated for believing that such a disease could be the result of evil spirits of darkness. The population of hospices was restricted to a portion of people who were marginalized, however, who were able to return to the social environment as productive subjects.

The first moment of madness in Brazil from the 16th to the 18th century, those affected by some kind of mental disorder were seen as people possessed by filthy, evil spirits that roamed the cities, being seen as people punished by the Divine for being considered heretics. European medicine did not obtain an exact conclusion for this illness that affected these people in that period of the 17th century; they thus associated disturbances with evil spirits without answers. Years later, the understanding of the disease changed and the methods used were revised and some were abandoned and only firming techniques remained, in contrast to aggression accompanied by cold baths, pain therapy, bloodletting, rotating machine, etc.

In the 19th century, exactly, in the year 1830, a newly arrived commission created by the Society of Medicine and Surgery of Rio de Janeiro carried out a diagnosis of the situation of madness in the State, since the disease was considered a disorder, something that disturbed social peace. , hampering the growth of the economy and the mercantilist and capitalist development of the country, which was still in great evolution. Considering that the insane aliens could not achieve the economic development of the current productive system, they were treated as waste by societies. “The new watchword appeared: the insane asylum” (MACHADO, 1978, sp). As a way of separating the unproductive from society, hospices and asylums were created.

Marked by negligence, discoveries, experiences, what draws attention are the trajectories and methods that were used with psychiatry and with the Brazilian individual, several techniques of visions considered common at the time intertwined with investigations about ethnicities, genders and mysticisms in search for the cause of madness in Brazil.

The history of psychiatry has always been linked to mysticism and beliefs. In the field of natural sciences it came to be considered as a disease related to the phase of the moon. In the 1920s, the disease was considered linked to hygiene issues and issues of social standards and even gender using the technique of removing the uterus in women, as they believed that the disease increased sexual libido and thus increased procreation and other they thought about race, believing that blacks and mestizos were more prone to diseases; thus characterized the thought of those who believed that the action of eugenics in the country as being the salvation for the entire race.

At the end of the 19th century, precisely in the year 1879, with the enactment of decree 7247 on April 19, assistance to madness began to be observed as a scientific discourse and more centered in the eyes of doctors. And *the Chair of Clinical Psychiatry* appears in courses at the Faculdade Médica in Rio de Janeiro and Bahia.

In 1890, with the Proclamation of the Republic, the Hospice of Pedro II is detached from the Santa Casa de Misericórdia and passes to the care of the public administration, which had its name changed to Hospício Nacional de Alienados, as well as its direction that was headed by João Carlos Teixeira Brandão (1854 - 1921) who modified the staff according to Machado (1978, p. 446) “removing the nuns and replacing them with lay nurses hired in Europe.”

According to Jerry Dávila (2005), “the reformist period began with two events: first, a team of doctors involved in the public health and hygiene movement in the country, left to map the health conditions in the interior of the country” (DÁVILA, 2005, p. 10).

In the period between 1902 and 1927, Juliano Moreira (1872-1933) was elected director of the National Hospital of the Insane, which had its name changed to Assistance to Psychopaths of the Federal District, bringing great humanistic developments to the treatment of the mentally ill. In the wake of this evolution,

It is worth noting the work of Dr. Nise da Silveira, developed at the CPPII since the 1940s. A focus of resistance from psychiatry existing at the time, the former STOR (Sector of Occupational Therapy and Rehabilitation) and later the Museum of Images of the Unconscious, was where Dr. Nise developed work based on Carl Gustav Jung's theory with patients hospitalized at the CPPII, bringing to light the contradictions of the psychiatric system and questioning its most resistant pillars; exclusion and violence (JORGE, 1997, p. 33).

After Juliano Moreira, there is no record in Brazil of any humanistic intervention in favor of the insane and insane, who are left to the inhuman conditions of the treatments intended for them in psychiatric hospitals and asylums. It is in this context of conditioning that the figure of Nise da Silveira (1905-1999) appears, who seeks to combine the technique of psychiatric treatment with artistic expression, allowing the insane to give vent to the images recorded in their unconscious minds.

At the Centro Psiquiátrico Nacional Pedro II, in place of the traditional cleaning and maintenance tasks that patients carried out under the heading of occupational therapy, she created painting and modeling workshops with the intention of enabling patients to reconnect with reality through expression. symbolism and creativity, revolutionizing the psychiatry then practiced in the country. The *Occupational Therapy Sector* was born there .

NISE DA SILVEIRA AND THE HUMANIZED ATTENTION TO CRAZY PEOPLE

Nise da Silveira was a historical character ahead of her time, a psychiatric doctor, a woman, fresh out of prison accused of the crime of subversion, she revolutionized psychiatric treatment, going against [almost] all of her professional colleagues and *big* names of the time.

Since her first contact with the formal psychiatric world, Nise da Silveira has faced resistance because of her confrontation with treatment methods dedicated to the mentally ill. This resistance, which could be added to the detail of being female, in a [*almost*] strictly male world, immediately condemned her to perform her duties in the Occupational Therapy department of Hospital Pedro II - RJ.

She entered the Medicine course at the Faculdade de Medicina da Bahia, at the age of 16, being the only female student to complete the course, among 157 other graduates in her

class. She was one of the first women to complete the course in the country and it can be added that she was also one of the first to attend a higher course in the history of the Nation, since its discovery.

Due to her Marxist orientations, she was denounced and arrested, being imprisoned along with Olga Benário and Graciliano Ramos. The latter, upon meeting Nise da Silveira during her imprisonment at the Frei Caneca Prison, wrote:

Elsewhere the meeting would give me pleasure. What I felt was surprise, I regretted seeing my fellow countrywoman out of the world, far from her profession, the hospital, her crazy loved ones. Knowledgeable and good, Rachel de Queirós had confirmed to me the moral greatness of that shy little person, always dodging, reducing herself, as if to excuse herself from taking up space. A friendlier creature had never appeared to me. Her husband, also a doctor, was my old acquaintance Mário Magalhães. I asked for news of him: he was free. And I fell silent, in a living Embarrassment (RAMOS, 2011, p. 105).

The issue of people with mental disabilities has become a matter of extreme relevance since there began to be a process of inclusion of these people in more socializing environments with a view to promoting a greater approximation of families, aiming at a recovery of the patient, through a more humanized or less exhausting treatment. Care for the mentally ill in Brazil has undergone severe changes since the work of Nise da Silveira, when work began on raising awareness and breaking myths and taboos, in which Occupational Therapy and art were sought to be merged, allowing patients to express their inner worlds through painting.

It is based on the works of Carl Gustav Jung about the unconscious and its manifestations and expressions and thus creates an expression technique that, with it, seeks to rescue the images of the unconscious, guaranteeing a certain balance of the patients' mental health, which collaborated for a process of their humanization.

According to Silveira (1981) “by applying Jung's discoveries to occupational therapy, new perspectives are opened for this method, both for neurotics and psychotics” (p. 06), allowing to open up the possibility of voice to those who found themselves excluded from life. social because of madness.

This action attracted the attention of experts, not only in psychiatry but also of plastic artists, which culminated in giving value to their work carried out for their patients. Foucault (1979) argues that the concepts of sanity and madness are social constructions that do not reflect quantifiable patterns of human behavior and that rather are only indicative of the power of the *healthy* over the insane.

According to him,

The practice of internment at the beginning of the 19th century coincided with the moment when madness was perceived less in relation to error than in relation to regular and normal conduct. Moment when it no longer appears as a disturbed judgment, but as a disorder in the way of acting, of wanting, of feeling passions, of making decisions and of being free. Finally, instead of being inscribed in the axis truth-error-consciousness, it is inscribed in the axis passion-will-freedom (FOUCAULT, 1979, p. 69).

Faced with the importance and centrality of care for individuals undergoing treatment and their subsequent resocialization and investigation into the deconstruction of ideologies about mental disabilities, there is an urgent need to detect their real needs, identifying the causes of their attitudes, that are often not understood, as well as the functioning of mental health care networks and support for patients with mental disorders by the institution where they are being treated.

The most interesting thing is that most of Nise da Silveira's work was carried out during the period called the *years of lead*, as it was the historical moment in which the country was under the command of the Military Government. This raises a very interesting question, namely that there was no persecution of these doctors because of their actions in relation to nervous patients.

All of Nise da Silveira's work in favor of the humanization of psychiatry and the treatment of the insane were carried out in public hospitals. Amarante (2007) points out that the more than three hundred years in which care for people with mental disorders was centered on psychiatric hospitals, left many consequences and suffering in the lives of thousands of people, since the deinstitutionalization process only began after many of these people have lived cloistered for decades, having their life projects and expectations reduced and/or eliminated.

There are alienated people whose delirium is almost imperceptible; there is not one in which the passions, the moral affections, are not disordered, perverted or annulled... The decrease of the delirium is only an effective sign of cure when the alienated return to their first affections. (Squirrel) What then is the healing process? The movement by which error dissipates and truth makes itself seen again? Absolutely, but rather "the return to moral affections within their just limits, the desire to see their friends, their children again, the tears of sensitivity, the need to open their heart, to be with their family, to resume their habits" (FOUCAULT , 1979, p. 69).

Amarante (2010) states that the experiences regarding the reformulation of psychiatric practices that occurred in Italy, England, France, USA and Brazil, are related and marked by common historical landmarks, such as the social demands of reorganization of the physical space and medicalization hospital.

According to JASPERS (sd) (*apud* GRUSPUM, 1961, p. 144) “mental weakness is a poor development of the spirit in all directions, from a weaker differentiation of thought, from a progressive variation of normal human dispositions to regions below average.”

From what has been explained above, it appears that mental disorder is the designation that characterizes problems that occur in the brain and lead to low performance, but that do not affect other regions or brain areas. It is known for problems that originate in the brain and cause low knowledge production, learning difficulties and a low intellectual level. Among the most common causes of this disorder are genetic factors, complications that occur during pregnancy or during childbirth and postnatal complications. The great enigma facing researchers is how to detect these characteristics while still in utero life. The fact is that the mentally ill are too heavy a burden for families to bear.

Possibly, Nise da Silveira's work marked a way of freeing individuals from their own subjective chains, weaving a deeper connection with the unconscious, with their private worlds, guided by the mentor. With the establishment of transformations in the psychiatric treatment model, seeking services that would overcome the deprivation of liberty of subjects with mental disorders, for daily psychosocial care services according to the needs of each user, it happens simultaneously with the search for the construction of a project of freeing the individual from a value judgment about his condition.

Jung stated that man lives in two distinct worlds, one of which is sensitive and the other unknown, and Nise da Silveira reveals that “in the psychotic condition, these two systems of perception often merge, internal space and external space interpenetrate. Plastic expression will make this psychological phenomenon visible through images of the painting studio itself” (1986, p. 15).

The author was in search of something that conventional psychiatry could never find in its objects of study and in systematic criticisms of Nise's work, they stated that as much as one wanted to see something real there, the image of human figures were distanced and even absent. . To this type of confrontation, she replied that, “if propositional language is functionally disarticulated in schizophrenia, speech in figures narrating a story will also be almost impossible and perhaps undesirable in the painter's sense. Another language then comes to assert itself, broader, not restricted to any conventions” (SILVEIRA, 1987, p. 26).

In 1941, Decree-Law No. 3,171, of April 2, created the National Mental Illness Service, with its central bodies: National Psychiatric Center, Juliano Moreira Colony and Judiciary Asylum. After 5 (five) years of the 1946 Constitution, marked by the country's democratization, the fundamental human rights were reestablished, in articles 129 to 144, with the express

provision of such rights, in the chapters referring to Nationality and Citizenship and Rights and Individual Warranties. Throughout history it can be observed that the changes did not evolve to the satisfaction of the citizens, but that it provided some comfort for the rulers, directly or indirectly (CARVALHO, 2005).

Nise carried out her work in the occupational therapy ward, until her retirement from professional life and, during the period of the Military Regime, she acted without suffering any sanction from the government. This is an interesting point to know, why the DOPS police (Department of Political and Social Order) did not interfere in the work of the psychiatrist.

A previous answer is that psychiatry performs a basic service that is very dear to absolute control regimes, which is to silence the subject considered insane. In this way, it was easy when you wanted to make a disaffected person fall into disgrace and public disbelief.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Psychiatry in Brazil follows models traced in European countries and treatments that were developed in reference countries were introduced without questioning their efficiency or effectiveness in terms of curing patients. Nise da Silveira raises her voice and creates a way of working that was restricted to Hospício Pedro II which was later transformed into the Museum of the Unconscious in the ways of seeing and treating the mentally ill, she was not persecuted by the DOPS police, in the period from 1964 to 1985, and it may be worth the idea that, as she was ignored by her peers, she was not the target of sanctions or aroused the concern of the regime.

In recognition of her work, she was awarded several decorations, titles and prizes in different areas of knowledge, among others: *Order of Rio Branco* , in the Official Degree, by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (1987); *The title of doctor honoris causa from the State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ)*, in 1988; *1992 Personality of the Year Award* from the Brazilian Association of Art Critics; *Chico Mendes Medal* , by the group Tortura Nunca Mais (1993); *National Order of Educational Merit* , by the Ministry of Education and Sports (1993).

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